

PURIFICATION OF THE MANGANESE OXIDIZING PROTEIN, MOPA-HP, FOUND IN
MARINE BACTERIUM *ERYTHROBACTER* SP. SD-21

by

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Abstract

Manganese (Mn) in both terrestrial and marine environments can be oxidized from soluble Mn^{2+} into insoluble $Mn^{3+/4+}$ by bacteria. The Mn oxides play an important role in the fate and biogeochemical cycling of vital elements such as carbon, sulfur, and iron. The Mn oxidation mechanism employed by bacterial enzymes is unclear, but with the potential to be utilized in the field of bioremediation. The marine bacterium *Erythrobacter* sp. SD-21 is known to produce a Mn-oxidizing protein, MopA (250-kDa) – a peroxidase cyclooxygenase. Previous purification attempts of the peroxidase domain, MopA-hp (105-kDa), have provided heterologously expressed samples with incomplete purification or no activity. The purpose of this project is to derive an active and pure sample of MopA-hp through different purification methods. The current purification protocol involves gravity nickel-affinity chromatography. Such a method has provided an active but not very pure sample of MopA-hp. Additional purification by anion exchange chromatography was investigated. The 105-kDa MopA-hp is identified by SDS-PAGE. The Mn oxidation activity is quantified through a colorimetric leucoberlin blue assay. A considerably pure sample of MopA-hp failed to oxidize Mn. A pure and active sample of MopA-hp will allow future studies on the mechanism of Mn oxidation implied by MopA-hp.

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Introduction

Mn Oxidation

Manganese (Mn) is an abundant transition metal found in both terrestrial and aquatic environments mainly in the form of Mn^{2+} (Tebo et al., 2005). A diverse group of microbes oxidize Mn^{2+} , into Mn^{3+} and Mn^{4+} (Miyata, 2007). Mn oxides are one of the strongest oxidants in the environment (Tebo et al., 2004). This is due to the valence electron configuration stability of Mn giving it a high redox potential (Tebo et al., 2018; Tebo et al., 2004). Although Mn has oxidation states from 0 to +7, the Mn species Mn^{2+} , Mn^{3+} , and Mn^{4+} are the most common on earth. Mn^{2+} is soluble, while Mn^{3+} and Mn^{4+} precipitate as oxides. Mn^{3+} is also very unstable in the absence of a chelator and would quickly gain or lose an electron (Oldham et al., 2017; Chinni et al., 2008).

Mn oxidation is thermodynamically favorable at low pH levels but at slow rates and it is accelerated by several orders of magnitude through the catalyzation of living organisms who have adapted to Mn oxidation (Cowan, 1996; Tebo et al., 2004). The oxidation of Mn^{2+} can affect the fate of other elements in the environment such as carbon, nitrogen, iron, copper, cobalt, lead, uranium, radium, and others (Tebo et al., 2018; Plathe et al., 2013). Thus, Mn oxides affect the different biological environmental processes that require such elements, and they also contribute to lowering levels of toxic substances in the environment (Tebo et al., 2004).

These traits categorize Mn oxidation as a great mechanism in the field of bioremediation (Tebo et al., 2004). In fact, its oxidation and dealkylation properties has allowed Mn oxidation to participate in the degradation of pharmaceutical drugs, PCBs, and atrazine (Sujith and Bharathi, 2011; Park et al., 1999; Cheney et al., 1998). Mn oxidation treatments have also been applied in wastewater filters and in the removal of toxins in waters and soil (Marcus et al., 2017). Although

Mn oxidation can be catalyzed by fungal and bacterial enzymes, only the mechanism implied by fungal enzymes has been well studied and applied for industrial purposes (Glenn and Gold, 1985; Wang, Yao, and Su, 2018; Gorbacheva et al., 2009).

Multicopper Oxidases

There is currently little understanding about bacterial enzymes catalyzing Mn oxidation in part due to difficulty in purifying the enzymes. Bacteria can oxidize Mn^{2+} by different bacterial enzymes such as multicopper oxidases (MCOs) and heme peroxidases. MCOs have been found in bacterial strains such as *Pseudomonas putida* MnB1 and GB-1, *Bacillus* sp. SG-1, and *Leptothrix discophora* -SS1 (Tebo et al., 2005). MCOs are a great electron receptor due to their four copper binding motifs that allow the distribution of electrons from Mn^{2+} into molecular oxygen (Kosman, 2017; Solomon, Sundaram, Machonkin, 1996; Bento, 2005). Although MCOs serve as a Mn oxidizing protein for some bacteria, they often do not have high specificity and can be responsible for the oxidation of organic compounds and other metals such as iron (Solomon et al., 1996; Vashchenko and MacGillivray, 2013). MCOs can be found in prokaryotes and eukaryotes and are also capable of detoxifying phenolic containing compounds (Singh, 2012).

Heme Peroxidases

Heme peroxidases are enzymes that catalyze Mn oxidation differently. These enzymes are divided into two different groups, the peroxidase cyclooxygenase and the peroxidase catalase superfamilies, and they contain a heme *b* cofactor (Zámocký, 2015; Zámocký, Furtmüller, and Obinger, 2010). Mn peroxidase (MnP), a manganese oxidizing protein, is part of the peroxidase catalase superfamily. This enzyme is found in white rot fungi such as *Pleurotus ostreatus* (Wariishi et al., 1992; Hirano et al., 2000). The mechanism implied by MnP consists of one

electron oxidation going from Mn^{2+} to Mn^{3+} . This Mn species can then oxidize phenolic (Abdel-Hamid, Solbiati, and Cann, 2013), and non-phenolic compounds (Qin et al., 2017) and plays an important role in lignin degradation.

MopA and MopA-hp

A novel heme peroxidase Mn-oxidizing protein in the superfamily of peroxidase cyclooxygenases, known as MopA, contains heme as a cofactor and has been found in the alphaproteobacteria *Aurantimonas manganoxydans* SI85-9A1, *Erythrobacter* sp. SD-21, and *Roseobacter* sp. AzwK-3b (Hansel, 2015; Anderson, et al., 2009). Heme enzymes can catalyze both oxidizing and reducing reactions between compounds. Heme enzymes that oxidate substrates are either oxygenases or peroxidases (Poulos, 2014). Yet, the oxidizing mechanism implied by MopA is still unclear.

The heterologous expression of the heme peroxidase domain, MopA-hp (approximately 105-kDa), from the 250-kDa native MopA, has led to partial purification of the protein. MopA-hp runs bigger in SDS-PAGE (~120 kDa) (Medina et al., 2018). Studies of full-length protein are difficult due to low expression of MopA in *Erythrobacter* sp. SD-21 and with heterologous expression in *E. coli*. A property of peroxidases includes the need of hydrogen peroxide as a substrate, but MopA does not require its presence for the oxidation of Mn^{2+} . The MopA-hp found in *Erythrobacter* sp. SD-21 requires the presence of calcium, heme, and NAD^+ for the oxidation of Mn^{2+} (Medina et al., 2018). Pyrroloquinoline quinone (PQQ) has been shown to serve as a stimulant for the manganese oxidation process (Johnson and Tebo 2007).

Heterologous expression of MopA-hp allows us to have an efficient purification of the manganese oxidizing protein for better characterization. The heme in MopA is theorized to be covalently bound and contains a histidine ligand that connected to an asparagine through

hydrogen bond formation, instead of the aspartic acid residue found in peroxidase catalases (Zeng & Fenna, 1992).

These discoveries and findings have helped the scientific community have a better understanding about the manganese oxidation process, but a full understanding of the biochemical mechanism of MopA requires a pure and active protein. Current research has either provided a pure but inactive MopA-hp or active but impure MopA-hp. This research focuses on the heterologous expression of MopA-hp in *Escherichia coli*, followed by exploring further purification of a MopA-hp using additional purification protocols.

Methods

Culture Maintenance

Fisherbrand Petri Dish, Slippable Lid 100mm x 15 mm sterile, polystyrene plates (Fisher Scientific) were prepared with Luria-Bertani (LB) broth media containing 60 µg/mL kanamycin (kan-60) and 30 µg/mL chloramphenicol (camp-30) (LB-kan-60, camp-30) for culture growth. A single colony of *Escherichia coli* Rosetta 2 pSpeedET-MopA-hp was streaked monthly into LB agar media plates containing kan-60 and camp-30 for culture maintenance.

Protein Expression

An overnight culture of *E. coli* Rosetta 2 pSpeedET-MopA-hp was prepared under sterile conditions in a 250 mL Erlenmeyer flask containing 50 mL of LB media, kan-60, and camp-30. A single colony was inoculated from an LB-kan-60, camp-30 plate was used to inoculate the overnight culture. The flask was placed on a shaker at 37°C overnight for approximately 12 to 16 hours. Then, under sterile conditions, 2-250 mL Erlenmeyer flasks were prepared with 100 mL of LB media, 100 µL of kan-60, 100 µL of camp-30, and 2 mL of overnight culture to each flask. These flasks were placed in a shaker at 37°C until the cultures reached an OD_{600nm} of 0.5, measured with a Varian Cary 50 Bio UV-Visible Spectrophotometer (approximately 2 hours). Once the desired optical density was reached, 200 µL of 10% L-Arabinose was added to each flask to induce expression. The flasks were then placed in a shaker at 37°C for 4 hours. To harvest the cells, the culture from one flask was placed into 2-50 mL sterile conical tubes (50 mL of solution to each tube). The same process was conducted for the other flask. The tubes were then centrifuged in a Sorvall Legend X1R Centrifuge (Thermo Scientific) at 4°C, 36221 × g, for 15 minutes. The supernatant was then removed and discarded. The cell pellets were resuspended

in 1.5 mL equilibrium (EQ) buffer [50 mM HEPES pH8, with 10 mM imidazole, and 50 mM NaCl]. The tubes were stored in a -20°C freezer.

Cell Lysis

A French pressing technique using a French Press Cell Disrupter (Thermo Electron Corporation) was conducted to lyse the cells and collect the cell-free extract (CFE). The resuspended cells were French pressed 3-4 times at about 16,000 psi. The CFE was separated from the non-lysed cells and cell debris in an Eppendorf Centrifuge 5430 R at 4°C for 5 minutes under $16,727 \times g$. Supernatant was collected and stored in the freezer at -20°C.

Purification by Gravity Nickel Affinity Chromatography

Gravity nickel (Ni) affinity chromatography (GNAC) was the first soluble cell extract purification protocol conducted. The Ni-immobilized metal affinity column chromatography contained 1 mL of nickel-nitrotriactic acid agarose beads. This column was washed with 5mL of MQ water, then 5 mL of EQ buffer, and incubated at 4°C in a rotator for 45 mins with 2 mL of CFE and 3 mL of EQ buffer. Unbound proteins were removed with 5 mL EQ buffer (Wash 1). The column was washed with 3 mL of Wash 2 buffer [50 mM Hepes pH 8, 300 mM NaCl, 20 mM imidazole, and 10% glycerol]. Protein was then eluted with 5 mL of Elution 1 buffer [50 mM Hepes pH 8, 300 mM NaCl, 40 mM imidazole, and 10% glycerol]. The column was cleaned with 5 mL of Elution 2 [20 mM Hepes pH 8, 300 mM NaCl, 300 mM imidazole, and 10% glycerol].

Buffer Exchange

The imidazole in the sample was removed from the purified protein by a PD-10 desalting column (GE healthcare) equilibrated with a dialysis buffer [20mM Hepes pH 8, 100mM NaCl, 10% glycerol]. 2.5 mL of gravity Ni affinity chromatography elution was added to the dialysis

buffer equilibrated column and the flow through was discarded. The column was washed with 1 mL of dialysis buffer. The MopA-hp protein was eluted once with 1.5 mL of dialysis buffer and a second time with 1 mL of same buffer.

Anion Exchange Chromatography

Further protein purification included anion exchange chromatography using a HiTrap™ Q XL 1 mL (Cytiva) column. This technique was conducted with a syringe and hand pressure. First the column was washed to remove preservatives with a syringe containing 5 mL of binding buffer (BB) [50 mM Tris-HCl pH 8 and 20% glycerol] followed by 5 mL of elution buffer (EB) [50 mM Tris-HCl pH 8, 20% glycerol, and 1 M NaCl]. Both buffers were filtered through a 0.45 µm syringe filter. 5 mL of BB was utilized for column equilibration before passing the MopA-hp-containing sample through the column. The MopA-hp-containing sample was filtered through a 0.22 µm syringe filter before placed in column. The column was then washed with 5 mL of BB to remove unbound proteins. Followed by a 5 mL wash of EB for analysis. This same process was repeated but in the presence of Avidin (Thermo Fisher), serving as a molecular crowding agent to help maintain protein activity. Avidin was mixed in BB with a concentration of 0.1 mg/mL (Johnson and Tebo, 2007) after the buffer was filtered. Avidin was not added to EB.

Sample Concentration

Concentrated samples were obtained through centrifugation in Amicon® Ultra-15 filter centrifuge tubes (Merck Millipore Ltd.) at $5,000 \times g$ for 20 minutes at 4°C.

SDS-PAGE

In order to confirm the presence and purity of MopA-hp in each sample obtained throughout all the steps, a sodium dodecyl sulphate-polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE) was conducted. The 2X stock solution (0.5 M TRIS pH 8.6, 10% SDS, 10% glycerol,

0.5% brophenol blue) mixed with 2-mercaptoethanol (1:20 dilution 2-mercaptoethanol) was utilized in a 1:1 ratio with the protein sample eluted. The SDS-PAGE was run at 200 constant volts. The dye utilized to colorize the bands in the gel consisted of 0.05% brilliant blue, 10% acetic acid, and 40% MeOH. The decolorizing solution consisted of 10% EtOH and 10% acetic acid.

MOP/LBB Assay

Samples containing MopA-hp were mixed in a ratio of 1:5 (500 μ L final volume) with a mixed solution containing 5 μ L of 0.1 M $MnCl_2$, 5 μ L of 1.0 M $CaCl_2$, 1 μ L of 5 mM PQQ, 383 μ L of 50 mM HEPES pH 8.0 + 100 mM NaCl, 5 μ L of 10 mM NAD^+ , and 1 μ L of 1 mM heme, for activity testing. The EQ buffer utilized before served as the negative control. Triplicates were conducted for each sample. After 24hrs of shaking at 200 rpm at room temperature, 50 μ L of the assay mixture was mixed in a ratio of 1:5 (250 μ L final volume) with 0.04% LBB in 45 mM acetic acid. After 15 minutes of shaking at 200 rpm at room temperature, these samples were centrifuged in an Eppendorf Centrifuge 5430 R for 5 minutes at $16,727 \times g$ at room temperature. The supernatant (250 μ L) was placed on a 96 well plate to read their absorbance at 620 nm on a Synergy 2 (Biotek) plate reader. The absorbance readings were compared to a standard curve produced with $KMnO_4$ standards where $1 \mu M KMnO_4 = 2.5 \mu M MnO_2$.

Protein Concentration

The absorbance at 280 nm was measured with a NanoDrop One^c (Thermo Scientific) to determine the protein concentration in the samples (A_{280} of 1 = 1 mg/mL protein). The baseline correction was 340 nm. The EQ buffer was utilized as a blank.

Results

Successful purification was determined by both SDS-PAGE, to visualize the 105 kDa MopA-hp and contaminating proteins, and by Mn oxidizing activity as measured with the LBB colorimetric assay. SDS-PAGE allowed for the confirmation of MopA-hp presence. Figure 1 presents all the samples collected from the GNAC purification protocol. At the 130-kDa mark, the presence of MopA-hp is confirmed in all the samples collected but at different intensities.

Figure 1. SDS-PAGE with samples eluted from GNAC.
 Lane 1: protein ladder.
 Lane 2: the flow through or unbound fractions.
 Lane 3: wash 1.
 Lane 4: wash 2.
 Lane 5: elution 1.
 Lane 6: elution 2.
 The samples were not concentrated prior to their SDS-PAGE analysis.

The sample collected from Elution 1 in GNAC was obtained for buffer exchange and further purification due to a combination between its purity level, as determined by SDS-PAGE (figure 1) and the Mn-oxidizing activity (Table 1). This sample provided the most promising results for the purpose of the project.

Table 1. MOP/LBB assay from the fractions obtained in GNAC protocol. The absorbance values correlate to the concentration of oxidized manganese. Averages of triplicate measurements.

MOP/LBB Assay A ₆₂₀						
Sample	Control	Flow Through	Wash 1	Wash 2	Elution 1	Elution 2
Average A ₆₂₀	0.000	0.522	0.253	0.004	0.244	0.752

After running the Elution 1 sample from GNAC through the buffer exchange protocol, another SDS-PAGE was conducted with all the samples collected (figure 2). The gel shows that MopA-hp is mostly present in fraction 2 and fraction 3.

Figure 2. SDS-PAGE with samples eluted from the buffer exchange protocol.

Lane 1: protein ladder.

Lane 2: the flow through of the buffer exchange protocol.

Lane 3: fraction 1.

Lane 4: fraction 2.

Lane 5: fraction 3.

These samples were not concentrated prior to their SDS-PAGE analysis.

Fraction 2 from the buffer exchange was used for further purification due to a combination of purity levels (figure 2) and protein activity (table 2). The sample collected in fraction 2 from the buffer exchange showed the highest protein activity.

Table 2. MOP/LBB assay from the fractions obtained from the buffer exchange. The absorbance values correlate to the concentration of oxidized manganese. Averages of triplicate measurements.

MOP/LBB Assay A ₆₂₀					
Sample	Control	Flow Through	Fraction 1	Fraction 2	Fraction 3
Average A ₆₂₀	0.000	-0.004	-0.005	0.696	0.471

The anion exchange chromatography (AEC) purification step was performed next, but it appeared unsuccessful at first. After the samples were concentrated (figure 3), a clear presence of MopA-hp was seen in both the BB and EB fractions. The BB fraction seems to have no purity level change from the buffer exchange, but the EB fraction appears to have a clean band of MopA-hp. Protein activity from these samples was not determined due to problems with the assay (table 3).

Figure 3. SDS-PAGE with the samples eluted from AEC.

Lane 1: protein ladder.
 Lane 2: the flow through from the chromatography process.
 Lane 3: BB fraction.
 Lane 4: EB fraction.
 Lane 5: concentrated BB fraction.
 Lane 6: concentrated EB fraction.

Table 3. MOP/LBB assay from the fractions obtained from the AEC. The absorbance values correlate to the concentration of oxidized manganese. Averages of triplicate measurements.

MOP/LBB Assay A ₆₂₀				
Sample	Control	Flow Through	BB	EB
Average A ₆₂₀	0.000	0.000	0.003	0.000

**The values obtained were not trusted. At the time, there were issues with the protein activity assay. Once issues were fixed, there were no attempts of reevaluating these samples for Mn oxidation activity.*

AEC was conducted again as a purification step but this time in the presence of Avidin (AECA) which was used as a molecular crowding agent to help maintain enzyme activity. The SDS-PAGE is similar to the SDS-PAGE for AEC without avidin (figures 3 and 4). In the presence of avidin, MopA-hp is mainly observed in the BB + avidin fraction as a clean and clear band. There is little to no presence of MopA-hp in the EB fraction even after being concentrated. Of note, the concentrated samples here were higher in volume at the end than those concentrated from AEC without avidin.

Figure 4. SDS-PAGE with the samples eluted from AECA.

Lane 1: protein ladder.

Lane 2: fraction 2 from buffer exchange.

Lane 3: the flow through in the chromatography process.

Lane 4: BB + avidin fraction.

Lane 5: EB fraction.

Lane 6: concentrated BB + avidin fraction.

Lane 7: concentrated EB fraction.

Unfortunately, the Mn oxidation activity assay indicated that all activity was lost (table 4). Even the sample containing the abundant MopA-hp band showed no Mn oxidation activity.

Table 4. MOP/LBB assay from the fractions obtained from the AECA. The absorbance values correlate to the concentration of oxidized manganese. Averages of triplicate measurements.

MOP/LBB Assay A_{620}				
Sample	Control	Flow Through	BB + Avidin	EB
Average A_{620}	0.000	-0.006	-0.004	-0.003

Discussion

Purification of MopA-hp

The purpose of this project was to derive an active and pure sample of MopA-hp after its heterologous expression in *E. coli*. One part of the objective was accomplished while the other requires the conduction of more studies. After multiple purification attempts, what appears to be a clean and clear band of MopA-hp in the presence of avidin was obtain. It took, running the CFE through a GNAC column, buffer exchange through a PD-10 desalting column, and another run through an AEC column with the presence of avidin to get there. See figure 5 for an overall SDS-PAGE analysis of the experiment.

Figure 5. SDS-PAGE compilation containing all the samples eluted for further analysis.

Lane 1: protein ladder.

Lane 2: CFE from cell lysis.

Lane 3: elution 1 from GNAC.

Lane 4: fraction 2 from buffer exchange.

Lane 5: concentrated BB fraction from AEC.

Lane 6: concentrated BB + avidin fraction from AECA.

Protein Activity

The other objective of the project was to keep MopA-hp active throughout the purification. This part of the project was partially accomplished (table 5). The experiment started with high activity readings from the CFE collected. A major drop in activity was observed in the Elution 1 from GNAC. The buffer exchange permitted an increase in protein activity. This was expected since,

as previously hypothesized, the removal of imidazole removes a competitor with the heme in solution (Medina et al., 2018). Lastly, the multiple elution collected from the AEC protocols, with or without avidin, reported no protein activity.

Table 5. MOP/LBB assay from the fractions obtained from the compilation of eluted samples for further analysis. The absorbance values correlate to the concentration of oxidized manganese.

Averages of triplicate measurements.

Mop/LBB Assay A ₆₂₀						
Sample	Control	CFE	GNAC	Buffer Exchange	AEC	AECA
Average A ₆₂₀	0.000	1.277	0.244	0.696	0.003	-0.004

*Same samples shown in figure 5.

Future Studies

Future work could focus on the further analysis of elution 2 from GNAC to compare final results to the elution 1 wash from GNAC. Another perspective to tackle the issue of protein activity would be to follow-up the Medina et al., 2018 mass spectrometry study and see which component is required to maintain Mn oxidizing activity by MopA-hp. Further purification of MopA-hp in the presence of avidin can be accomplished by size exclusion chromatography. A final characterization of MopA-hp and the compounds that allow for its activity, plus a pure sample of it, would allow for kinetic studies of MopA-hp and thus have a better understanding of MopA-hp and its mechanism implied in Mn oxidation.

Appendix

All the samples selected for further analysis were also tested for protein concentration in solution (table 6). Only the fraction collected from AECA, BB + avidin, was tested after the sample was concentrated. The rest were tested as they were collected.

Table 6. Protein concentration analysis of all the samples selected for further analysis. The absorbance values correlate to the protein concentration present in sample.

Protein Concentration A ₂₈₀						
Sample	Control	CFE	Elution 1 (GNAC)	Fraction 2 (Buffer Exchange)	BB (AEC)	BB + Avidin (AECA)
mg/mL	0.000	32.383	0.225	0.202	0.072	2.304
A ₂₈₀	0.000	32.380	0.230	0.200	0.070	2.30

Also, important to note, protein activity from fraction 2 of the buffer exchange in the presence of avidin was tested. It was not possible to obtain a conclusive statement about avidin and its effect on protein activity due to its presence in solution. Data collected was not considered reliable since the activity assay started showing issues right after the analysis was conducted (table 7). This test was conducted to double check previous study showing that avidin helps maintain Mn-oxidizing protein activity (Johnson and Tebo, 2007).

Table 7. MOP/LBB assay to test the effect of having avidin present in solution with active MopA-hp from fraction 2 (buffer exchange). The absorbance values correlate to the concentration of oxidized manganese. Averages of triplicate measurements.

MOP/LBB Assay A ₆₂₀			
Sample	Control	Fraction 2 (Buffer Exchange) + Avidin	Fraction 2 (Buffer Exchange)
Average A ₆₂₀	0.000	0.028	0.024

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